

From Labelled Surveys to Label-Scarce Cities: a Hybrid Activity Labelling with Iterative User Profiling Approach

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Summary

In recent years, large-scale human mobility data have been widely used to support urban and transport analysis. However, these data are often released without semantic labels (e.g., activity purpose and travel mode), which limits users' ability to derive deeper insights for urban analysis. Although supervised methods can achieve stable semantic labelling when dataset-specific ground truth is available, such ground truth is rarely accessible in real-world applications, and cross-dataset transfer from external labelled sources often results in substantial performance loss. To address this issue, we propose a novel hybrid pipeline that (i) learns per-stay activity probabilities from a labelled GPS travel survey, (ii) enforces temporal consistency via HMM/Viterbi smoothing, and (iii) iteratively refines labels using user-level profile priors estimated from long-horizon, high-confidence predictions. This approach stabilizes rare classes and reduces place-level inconsistencies at frequently visited locations.

When evaluated on the test set, it outperforms single-component baselines, including rule-based, HMM, and ML-classifier methods, and more accurately reproduces hourly dynamics and daily motifs. When transferred to a label-scarce London subset, the model improves semantic stability and yields OD-ready home/work anchors for commuting analyses.

KEYWORDS: urban mobility analysis, passive GPS data, activity patterns, commuting and OD flows, user profiling.

1 Introduction

In recent years, it has seen a rapid growth in large-scale human mobility data, such as GPS data, providing high spatio-temporal resolution behavioral evidence for transport and urban studies, from commuting and accessibility to equity, urban functionality, and policy evaluation. However, unlike traditional household travel surveys, such data are typically released without semantic labels (e.g.,

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activity purposes), limits users’ ability to derive deeper insights for urban analysis. While a rich literature exists on activity labelling (Yin et al., 2021; Sari Aslam et al., 2021; Meng et al., 2017; Gao et al., 2021; Ermagun et al., 2017), many high-performing machine learning and deep learning approaches depend on carefully annotated, domain-matched labelled datasets—a requirement that is difficult to meet for large-scale, privacy-preserving GPS traces in real-world settings.

A practical approach is rule-based labelling. Such methods typically leverage home/work anchors, POI-based spatial context, and temporal heuristics to assign semantic activity labels to stay locations, such as shopping, leisure, education, and other purposes. Recent work on anonymised human location data in England (Zhong et al., 2025) shows that such approaches can reproduce stable aggregate patterns when benchmarked against official statistics. However, rule-based methods have limited ability to capture sequential patterns, account for how activity type depends on when, where, and how long a person stays, or keep labels consistent over time, especially for less frequent classes. In real-world applications, a further practical need is to identify one primary home and one primary work location for each user, so that commute OD pairs can be extracted regardless of the labelling method used.

Existing approaches, including rule-based heuristics, sequential inference, and supervised learning, are each insufficient to address label scarcity on their own. To tackle this issue, we propose a hybrid pipeline with four components. First, we model activity sequences using an HMM, where transition probabilities are conditioned on contextual factors such as weekday/weekend and broad time-of-day categories. We then use Viterbi decoding to obtain temporally coherent labels and reduce fragmented predictions. Second, we train a supervised per-stay classifier on an external GPS travel survey from Paris. It estimates activity probabilities for each stay based on temporal, spatial, and POI-derived features. Third, we incorporate these probabilities into the HMM emission model. In this way, the framework combines stay-level discriminative evidence with sequential smoothing. Fourth, we derive user-level activity profiles from long-horizon, high-confidence predictions and use them as soft priors to improve consistency in the inferred labels. We then consolidate the results into one primary home anchor and one primary work anchor for each user, producing OD-ready outputs for commute analysis.

2 Data and Problem Setting

We use two privacy-preserving GPS datasets for different purposes: a labeled Paris dataset for supervised training and validation, and a label-scarce UK dataset for evaluation. The first is a Paris GPS survey dataset with ground-truth activity purposes, released for the NetMob25 data challenge (Chasse et al., 2025). It covers 3,337 participants in the Île-de-France region and contains one week of high-frequency GNSS traces with validated trip annotations. An anonymisation pipeline is applied (e.g., pseudonymisation and independent trip-endpoint blurring using H3), which may introduce day-to-day jitter in inferred home/work anchors.

The second dataset is a long period, passively collected UK GPS dataset licensed from Locomizer, a UK-based data provider. The company aggregates mobile GPS data from roughly 200 apps and supplies pre-processed records (e.g., anonymisation via cryptographic hashing, noise filtering, and

aggregation) to comply with GDPR and contractual obligations. To minimize ethical privacy risks, we use only a minimal set of attributes, broadly comparable to those available in other primary streaming mobility data sources, such as smart-card or social media traces.

In the current experiments, we focus on users in the London region. Semantic activity labels are unavailable, and any vendor-provided tags are considered unreliable, which motivates a label-scarce strategy. We label stays using a unified seven-class taxonomy: HOME, WORK, STUDY, PURCHASE, LEISURE, HEALTH, and OTHER.

To keep the spatial context features consistent across Paris and the UK, we derive Points of Interest from Ordnance Survey POI data in the UK and from OpenStreetMap POIs in Geofabrik exports for Paris. These POIs are mapped into coarse categories and aggregated using a consistent Huff-style buffer approximation. The Paris dataset supports supervised training and validation under a user-level 80/20 split, whereas the UK setting is evaluated through label-scarce diagnostics and behavioural summaries.

3 Proposed Method

Our method is designed to turn raw stay sequences into semantic activity labels and stable home/work anchors that can be used for further human mobility analysis. It uses information from three aspects: the timing and duration of stays, the surrounding spatial context represented by nearby POIs, and candidate home/work locations inferred from repeated patterns in the same user’s stay history, especially during night-time and typical working hours.

This structure design reflects a practical challenge in urban mobility analysis under label scarcity. Rule-based methods can be applied even when no ground truth is available in the target dataset, but they often remain too rigid to capture how activity meaning depends jointly on when, where, and how long people stay. Sequence models such as HMMs help impose temporal order and reduce implausible switching between labels, but they still rely heavily on manually specified stay-level evidence and may be sensitive to differences in POI coverage and urban context. Supervised classifiers, by contrast, can learn richer decision boundaries from labelled data, yet their predictions may not transfer cleanly across cities and may become unstable over long observation periods. We therefore combine stay-level supervised prediction, sequence-based smoothing, and long-horizon consistency checks in a single framework.

The proposed pipeline has four components:

- **Sequential modeling with HMM and Viterbi decoding.** We represent activities as a latent state sequence. The transition matrices $A^{(c)}$ are conditioned on broad contextual settings (weekday/weekend \times coarse time-of-day bins). We then use Viterbi decoding to recover temporally coherent activity sequences and reduce fragmented labels.
- **Stay-level supervised classification.** We train a supervised classifier on the Paris dataset to estimate activity probabilities $p_t(a)$ for each stay location. The input features include stay start time and duration, Huff-style POI features, and spatial features defined relative

to inferred anchors and recent movement (e.g., distances to home/work and to the previous stay).

- **Combining stay-level predictions with sequence decoding.** We incorporate the classifier outputs into the HMM emission terms:

$$\log B_t(a) = \frac{1}{T} \log (p_t(a) + \epsilon), \quad (1)$$

and then apply Viterbi decoding with $A^{(c)}$. This step combines stay-level discriminative evidence with sequential smoothing.

- **User-profile refinement and anchor consolidation.** We estimate a user-specific activity profile $\pi_u(a)$ from high-confidence predictions over a long observation period, and use it as a soft prior:

$$\log B_t(a) \leftarrow \log B_t(a) + \lambda \log (\pi_u(a) + \epsilon), \quad (2)$$

to improve label consistency over time. We then identify one primary home anchor and one primary work anchor for each user based on the dominant spatial cluster, and reassign non-primary HOME/WORK labels to OTHER so that the final outputs can be used directly for OD analysis.

4 Experiments and Results

We evaluate on Paris (labeled) and apply to London-region UK data (label-scarce). For Paris, we perform a user-level 80/20 split into training and validation sets to avoid leakage across days. We compare four variants reflecting the methodological progression: **Rule-based** labeling (home/work anchors, POI spatial context, and temporal heuristics), an **HMM** with sequence-aware decoding, a supervised **Gradient Boosted Decision Trees, GBDT** per-stay classifier (no sequential smoothing), and the **Hybrid** model combining GBDT likelihoods with HMM/Viterbi smoothing (with temperature $T=0.5$). Paris performance is reported with ACC, Macro-F1, and Macro-F1 excluding HOME (Macro_weak); given substantial class imbalance (rare STUDY/HEALTH), we emphasise Macro_weak. We additionally report behavioural summaries (daily motifs and hourly distributions). For UK, we report label-scarce diagnostics (night-home share, home/work anchor entropy, switch rate) and commuting-oriented proxies on weekdays.

Paris (ground-truth). Table 1 shows that the Hybrid model achieves the best overall balance, with the highest Macro_weak. Feature ablations (Table 2) indicate that POI context and anchor/movement geometry provide complementary gains for per-stay prediction, and Fig. 1 summarises incremental improvements across modelling components. Motif comparisons (Fig. 2) provide an interpretable check on daily activity structure relative to ground truth.

UK (label-scarce transfer). UK motif distributions (Fig. 3) reveals systematic differences across models: sequence-aware variants (HMM/Hybrid) produce more coherent workday structure than sequence-free GBDT transfer. Label-scarce diagnostics indicate that iterative self-profiling improves spatial-semantic stability: night-home share remains high while home/work anchor entropy and

Table 1: Paris validation performance (user-level split).

Model	ACC	Macro-F1	Macro_weak
Rule-based	0.442	0.310	0.251
HMM	0.575	0.420	0.360
GBDT (no smoothing)	0.627	0.491	0.428
Hybrid (GBDT+HMM)	0.669	0.513	0.450

Table 2: Feature ablation for the supervised per-stay classifier (GBDT).

Setting	ACC	Macro-F1	Macro_weak
Base (time+duration)	0.481	0.393	0.336
Base + POI	0.538	0.440	0.390
Base + anchor-dist	0.574	0.438	0.371
Base + POI + anchor-dist	0.615	0.480	0.418
All (+prev-dist)	0.627	0.491	0.428

switch rate decrease (Table 3). Primary anchor consolidation yields unique OD-ready home/work anchors by absorbing secondary/temporary locations into OTHER.

5 Discussion and Conclusion

This work makes unlabeled GPS/stay data more usable for transport and urban mobility analysis by producing coherent activity sequences, interpretable behavioral summaries, and stable primary home/work anchors for OD analysis. These outputs support applications such as commuting analysis, tracking behavioral change under interventions, and examining accessibility and equity by linking inferred activities to neighborhood context.

A key limitation is the robustness of cross-domain transfer beyond London, especially across regions with different mobility cultures, POI classification systems, sampling characteristics, and privacy-preserving transformations. Future work should develop more principled transfer strategies, including calibration-based adaptation and region-specific priors, extend the framework to broader UK coverage, and establish clearer links between labelled GPS outputs and comparable public benchmarks. Overall, the proposed pipeline offers a reproducible way to move from label-scarce GPS data to consistent activity patterns and commute-related indicators under real-world data constraints.

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Figure 1: Paris validation: incremental gains in Macro_weak (Macro-F1 excluding HOME) across modelling components.

Table 3: UK label-scarce diagnostics (London users, 1-week window).

Method	Night-home share (mean)	Home entropy (mean)	Work entropy (mean)	Switch rate (day-avg)
Hybrid (GBDT+HMM)	0.980	0.150	0.344	1.813
Hybrid + self-profile	0.983	0.124	0.295	1.798

expertise in data handling and real-world use cases of spatial analytics, which enhanced the quality of this study. The authors thank ChatGPT (OpenAI) for assistance with English grammar correction and wording refinement during manuscript preparation. All ideas, analyses, and conclusions are those of the authors.

7 Biography

Dr Yanbo Pang is a research Fellow at the Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis, UCL. His work focusing on developing synthetic mobility using large-scale GPS, mobile phone, and statistical data with GeoAI. His work combines geospatial data science, urban modelling, agent-based simulation, and LLMs to support digital twins, transport planning, and urban policy evaluation.

Dr Chen Zhong is a professor of urban analytics at the Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis, UCL. Her work focuses on leveraging human location data, advanced spatial analysis, and modelling to address transport-related challenges, including socio-spatial inequalities, decarbonisation, and the applicability of analytical methods across diverse urban contexts.

Mr Zhengzi Zhou is a PhD candidate at the Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis, UCL. He studies urban mobility, spatial segregation, and place geometry, examining how urban form shapes

Figure 2: Paris validation: daily activity motifs (top patterns) comparing ground truth and model outputs.

Figure 3: UK 1W: daily motifs across models (label-scarce comparison).

movement and inequality. Using mobility data, network modularity, deep learning, and complexity models, he reveals hidden structures and barriers to inform evidence-based planning and policy.

Mr Yikang Wang is a final-year PhD candidate at the Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis, UCL. He develops spatial causal inference for transport planning using mobile phone app location data. He co-chairs GISphere, a non-profit promoting global GIS education.

Mr Adham Enaya is a PhD candidate at the Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis, UCL. He focuses on urban transfer learning and a Research Fellow in AI for collective intelligence in smart cities. He develops machine-learning methods that adapt across cities, combining urban data, to support smarter, more inclusive decision-making.

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